

How to register an organization/Firm/Company/Institution in Nepal, based on Laws?

A Legal Framework, for any any legal entity.

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Note: Mental Asylum of Education has applied for registration in Office of Company Registrar Registration, and has temporary ID 1112392. This article, is intended to be submitted as Annual report to Office of Company Registrar Registration, and Courts, as per application submitted by Mental Asylum of Education. Author mostly relies on comma(,), and or, thus do thinks, readers would read, like as of verbal communication. In terms of publication, that would be like as proof-reading, or even reading out loud, or reading silently

Abstract: In english language, we use words like as Firm, organization, institution, company in conviniently synonymously. However, In Nepal, as per Laws, all do have seperate Acts, and Departments for registration, whereas flexibility is provided by Laws, to work, as per Laws. Thus we have discussed about general outlines, for registration(though author does doubts, if any company/firm/organization/institution would be able to registered or not, as per the following procedures). Slash(/) written indicates Or.

Introduction:

Firm, organization, company institution, or any business entity either be profit based or non-profit based, had to begin, from defining their administrative body.

For private firm based on individual operation; just a application letter is needed, as per Laws, which too has provided sample application letter, to be followed while registering. It isn't necessary to follow exactly same (though administrative officials would demand, that might be as per their learning, from acts, which would be another humour too), as in generality experience and learning from older(much experienced fellows in any particular department) is seen.

Registration Process:

Trademarks are important topics, of any firm/institution/organization/company, and are mentioned in acts, as well as sample applications. For private individual firm, individuals would need to submit application to Department of Industry, in Intellectual Property section. That is formally, and legally needed, to provide validation, authentication, and recognition, to logo/symbol or any Trademarked topics, relating to any entity.

When it comes to registration of Organization, or an company, then as per Widhaan(constitution) of any organization; or Prawandhapatra, and Niyamawali (Like as Definition, and working procedures for execution of work based on guidelines, and similiar to constitution), again Logo/Stamp/Symbols, relating to Trademark are needed.

Either Trademark are registered before registration of any organization; or after registration of any organization, would then define Trademark, allowing for use of Stamps and Logo.

Constitution: Any organization are free to make constitution, as per their administrative body, based on Laws. That is same for institution/company, where objectives are needed to be provided. That would mean, any organization would be allowed to work, as per their objectives, which are based on NSIC (Nepal Standard Industrial Classification) code. NSIC codes are like same as ISO codes in international sector. Based on those codes, objectives are defined, on basis of which, any organization/company/institution does works. Sample of Cosntitution can be found in respective websites of Departments.

Intellectual Property: After registration of any firm/company/organization/institution, based on consitution, intellectual property can be registered in Office of copyright registrar registration. That would provide copyright to comstitution (and might provide to all intellectual property). Then comes topics of website, which too has to be registered, in Department of Information, or other departments. That is because, website too does provides information, irrespective of contents in websites.

Permissions: After registration too, based on objectives, permissions have to be taken from respective departments. For an example, registering as organization in District Administrative Office, would further need permission, after registration, and same is for registration of any company in office of company registrar registration.

Flexibility:

Laws does allows flexibility, based on acts, and based on need. An application letter can be submitted, to respective departments, or Courts, if any provisions are needed. Application letter, can be either in form of Writ application, or general application.

Actknowledgements

My actknowledgement goes to all administrative bodies, their websites, and Laws(Acts) of Nepal. Acts are different then that of constitution.